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A Concise Historiography of Classical Yoga Philosophy*

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1. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

The literary production of works on yoga is vast, and it increases constantly. This large output reflects on the one hand the quest of modern (or, according to one's own stand point, post-modern) globalized societies for supplements and alternatives to their own religious and/or secular traditions. The thriving yoga literature is a symptom for the growing acculturation of modern yoga into globalized societies, for which the existence of yoga studios at almost every second corner of the streets in cities of many parts of the world provides additional evidence.

The global yoga boom was neither initiated nor appropriately accompanied in its development by academic research. Its historical roots lie not in European scholarship but rather in the encounter of modern western cultures with the post-traditional societies in South-Asia, for which the British colonization of the Indian sub-continent provided the stage. As Singleton has shown recently (2010), modern *āsana*-oriented yoga developed from a blend of the views of European bodybuilding and gymnastic movements with Indian nationalism and political Hinduism as well as obscure indigenous yoga traditions. These political conceptions oscillated between a fascination for modern western ideas and a self-affirming appraisal

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of the Hindu religious and philosophical traditions, among which the philosophical ideas of Advaita Vedānta played a prominent role.

Vivekānanda, the early and influential spokesman of Neo-Hinduism, developed his own Yoga philosophy on the basis of the root text of a classical philosophical school of Yoga, the Yoga Sūtra of Patañjali. For that matter, he furnished his “Rāja Yoga” (1896) with an edition of the Yoga Sūtra in *devanāgarī* script together with a translation (or rather: a free paraphrase) of the Sanskrit original. He provided his rendering with his own commentary, in which he separated the meaning of the Yoga Sūtra completely from its original cultural and historical context (see De Michelis 2004: 149-178). This approach set a precedent, which was followed in many general and semi-academic publications that appeared during the next approximately 115 years.¹

Paul Deussen, for example, applied a similarly ahistorical approach to his study of Yoga in his “Allgemeine Geschichte der Philosophie (General history of philosophy)” (Deussen 1908). He chose the Yoga Sūtra, which he regarded as a compilation of four or five originally independent works, as the only source for his exposition of Yoga philosophy (Deussen 1908: 509) and favoured a text-immanent interpretation over the interpretations of the commentaries.² Deussen turned for help to the Indian commentaries only when he could not understand the texts themselves by his own standards (see Deussen 1908: 510). Deussen did not – and in fact did not have to – bother with the question of how he could find sufficient information for a text-immanent approach in four or five originally independent works, which consist of only a few (between sixteen and eighty-three) brief phrases, apparently because he knew the original meaning of the Yoga Sūtra in advance.

¹ In academic writing, this approach is usually designed as research in the “original” or “essential” meaning of yoga to which the authors claim to have private access. Two typical examples for this method are Chapple 1994 and Witcher 1998.

² Hauer (1958: 224-239) developed a similar and equally unsatisfactory method, in which he divided the Yoga Sūtra into a number of independent *sūtra*-compositions on the basis of text-immanent considerations. Hauer’s translation (or rather: paraphrase) of the text combines his interpretation with his personal experience (p. 465); on this approach see also the review of Hauer’s work by Hacker (1960).

More than seventy years before Vivekānanda published his “Rāja Yoga”, Henry Thomas Colebrooke had applied a different approach to Yoga philosophy.³ Instead of using classical Yoga as a canvas for the projection of new philosophical and religious ideas, he set out to investigate what Indian philosophy could accomplish in its own right. His now famous essay “On the philosophy of the Hindus. Part 1: Sāṅkhya” (Colebrooke 1827) was not only one of the “first results of modern Indological research,” (Halbfass 1990: 84) but arguably the first academic publication on Yoga philosophy based on primary Sanskrit sources – in this case on manuscripts – at all.

Professor David Gordon White was kind enough to draw my attention to the earlier work of the missionary William Ward. In his publication with the title “*A View of the History, Literature and Religion of the Hindoos,*” Ward provides a brief account of yoga practice that he claims to be based on the “Patñjölü Dürshana and the Gorükshü Sünghita” (i.e. the Pātañjala Darśana and Gorakṣa Samhitā; Ward 1815: vi), but his exposition does not indicate an intimate knowledge of philosophical Yoga. In the first edition of his work (Ward 1811), which appeared under the title “*Account of the Writings, Religion and Manners of the Hindoos,*” and which is more comprehensive than the second one, Ward provides a brief account of *aṣṭāṅga*-yoga based on information by Indian paṇḍits. The two main yoga-sources, according to Ward’s unnamed informants, are the “Patñjölü-sootrü and the Bhözü-dāvü-dhṛttü-bhashyü” (i.e. the Pātañjala Sūtra and Bhoja’s Rājamārtaṇḍa; Ward 1811: 345).

Colebrooke was, however, not very favourably disposed towards Yoga philosophy.⁴ On the contrary; his verdict is that Yoga and Sāṅkhya, its sister philosophy

differ, not upon points of doctrine, but in the degree in which exterior exercises, or abstruse reasoning and study, are weighted upon, as requisite preparations of absorbed contemplation. PATANJALI’S Yóga-sástra is occupied with devotional exercise and mental abstraction, subduing body and mind: CAPILA is more engaged with investigation of principles and reasoning upon them. One is more mystic and fanatical. The other makes a

³ For the life and work of H.T. Colebrooke, see, for example, Windisch 1917-1920, vol. 1: 26-36, which is based on Colebrooke 1873. A new monograph on Colebrooke by Ludo and Rosane Rocher appeared while the present paper was in the press (Rocher – Rocher 2012).

⁴ Cf. also for the following part of section one of the present paper, White (forthcoming).

nearer approach to philosophical disquisition, however mistaken in its conclusion (Colebrooke 1827: 38).

According to Colebrooke, Sāṅkhya and Yoga share a common concern for “absorbed contemplation,” but they differ with regard to the degree in which they can be judged as philosophical thinking. Whereas Yoga is more concerned with exterior and devotional exercises, i.e. with practice, and therefore is hardly philosophy at all, Sāṅkhya is closer to Colebrooke’s standard of philosophical reasoning, i.e. it is more theoretical. The latter system is therefore preferable to Colebrooke, even though he takes its philosophical results to be “mistaken.”

This verdict apparently was the first articulation of a general attitude towards Yoga philosophy in Indology that remained influential to the present day. According to this preconception, everything philosophically important in Yoga is Sāṅkhya philosophy, and everything in Yoga that is different from Sāṅkhya is philosophically unimportant.⁵

As we have seen above, research in Yoga philosophy started under difficult conditions. On the one hand, early Indological research was at best not particularly interested in Yoga. This attitude was clearly in line with the negative presentation of yogis in early European travel accounts of India, as well as with the negative view of European scholarship towards the practice of *hatha* yoga.⁶ On the other hand, theosophical and esoteric circles appreciated yoga enthusiastically, but did not care for its philosophy in its cultural and historical setting.

How did Indological research develop under these difficult starting conditions? What is the present state of research, and what are the most urgent future tasks? The following part of this essay sketches major developments from the beginning of historical re-

⁵ Cf. Torella (2010: 91): “I have been strongly tempted to omit any treatment of Yoga in a work such as this, devoted essentially to the ‘philosophy’ of India. I should have also been in good company, considering that Indian tradition itself tends to treat Yoga mainly as a practice grafted onto conceptual assumptions provided by Sāṅkhya.” The passages of the Mahābhārata which Torella quotes in support of his assessment cannot refer to Sāṅkhya and Yoga as philosophical systems, since these systems did not even exist at the time of the composition of the Great Epic.

⁶ See Singleton 2010: 35-53.

search in Yoga philosophy to the present date. Its main aim is to describe the major steps of Indological research by highlighting the more important works in European languages and to define the direction in which a fruitful future development is to be expected.⁷ Before I address this topic, I shall, however, re-address the question of the authorship of the foundational work of Yoga philosophy, the Pātañjala Yogaśāstra. I shall summarize previous research on this topic and contribute a few new arguments by drawing upon two sources of information: (a) external evidence in the form of references to this work in comparatively early Sanskrit and Arabic literature, and (b) text immanent evidence.

2. PATAÑJALI AND THE AUTHORSHIP OF THE PĀTAÑJALA YOGAŚĀSTRA

Many handbooks of Sanskrit literature and modern histories of Indian philosophy published in the last approximately 110 years contain an overview of the available primary sources of classical Yoga philosophy. What we read there is that Patañjali was the author of a work called Yoga Sūtra, and that this was glossed by an author named Vyāsa or Vedavyāsa in a commentary called Yoga Bhāṣya.⁸

As was noticed by Jacobi (1929: 584), Venkatarama Raghavan (1938-1939: 84), Bronkhorst (1985: 203f.) and Maas (2006: xivf.), however, there are a number of comparatively early primary Sanskrit sources, dating from the tenth century onwards, which contradict this common view. Śrīdhara, Abhinavagupta, Hemacandra, Viṣṇubhaṭṭa, Śivopādhyāya and Devapāla all refer to *bhāṣya* passages as having been composed by Patañjali.⁹ All these authors indicate that the

⁷ The selection of works presented here was, of course, guided by subjective criteria. Moreover, due to limitations of space and time, the survey remains necessarily incomplete. A much broader bibliographical overview of yoga research is presented in Schreiner 1979. A comprehensive online bibliography of Indian philosophy including Yoga is offered by Karl H. Potter at <http://faculty.washington.edu/kpotter/> (accessed in October 2012).

⁸ See for example Dasgupta 1922-1955, vol. 1: 212, Frauwallner 1953: 288, Garbe 1896: 40f., Hiriyanna 1932: 270, Renou – Filliozat 1953: 45f., Strauss 1925:178 and 191, Tucci 1957: 99, and Winternitz 1922: 460 f.; cf. – also for the following paragraphs – Maas 2006: xii-xix.

⁹ In all cases, we find citations of *bhāṣya*-passages ending with the statement *iti patañjaliḥ*.

Pātañjala Yogaśāstra (i.e. the *sūtra* passages together with the *bhāṣya* part of the work) is a unified whole that was possibly composed by one single author.

The earliest reference to the Pātañjala Yogaśāstra (PYŚ) as a standard work on Yoga occurs in the commentary of Vṛṣabhadeva (ca. 650 CE.) on Bhartṛhari's Vākyapadīya.¹⁰ Acquaintance with the PYŚ seems to have been widespread not only among the philosophers of that time but also among the educated general public. This can be concluded from the description of yogic meditation in stanza 4.55 of Māgha's Śīsupālavadhā (datable to ca. 750 CE at the latest, but possibly one or two centuries earlier, see Kane 1914: 91-95), which betrays intimate knowledge of the work on the side of the author as well as on the side of the audience being addressed (Hultzsich 1927).

The assessment that the PYŚ is a single work with a single author is corroborated by the wording of the critically edited version of all four chapter colophons of the PYŚ in the twenty-five manuscripts that I used for my critical edition of the first chapter of the PYŚ. These colophons indicate that the oldest reconstructable title of the work was *pātañjalayogaśāstra sāṅkhyapravacana* “the authoritative exposition of yoga that originates from Patañjali, the mandatory Sāṅkhya teaching (*pravacana*).”

The PYŚ neither contains separate chapter colophons nor a final colophon for its *sūtra* part. References to the title *yogabhāṣya* and to the author's name Vyāsa or Vedavyāsa are only transmitted in a few manuscripts of limited stemmatic relevance. Originally the work had neither the title *yogabhāṣya* nor did it contain the personal name Vyāsa (see Maas 2006: xvf. and xxf.).

The Yoga Sūtra appears to have no manuscript transmission independent of that of the PYŚ, because the manuscripts of the Yoga Sūtra I have seen so far consist of extracts from the PYŚ only. Variants exist only with regard to the inclusion or omission of single, introductory words of the *sūtras*, like *tatra*, *kimca* etc. Some scribes of the Yoga Sūtra took these to be part of the text, whereas others regarded these adverbs as part of the *bhāṣya* and did not include them

¹⁰ Vṛṣabhadeva glosses the word *adhyātmaśāstrāṇi* “authoritative teachings on the inner self” of his basic text with *pātañjalādīni* “[authoritative teachings] like that of Patañjali” (see Maas 2006: xvii).

in their version of the *sūtra*. The same is true for the text of the printed editions listed by Meisig (1988: 53). All variant readings Meisig records for the first chapter of the Yoga Sūtra result from different approaches of the scribes/editors in separating *sūtras* from their surrounding *bhāṣya*. Substantial variants in the *sūtra* text do not exist. A final verdict could, of course, be only made on the basis of a critical edition of the Yoga Sūtra, but the brevity of the text makes reliable text-critical research virtually impossible.

The author of the oldest commentary on the PYŚ, the Pātañjalayogaśāstravivarāṇa (cf. below, p. 75), also did not take Vyāsa to be the author of the *bhāṣya* passages. Whenever he makes a distinction between the two textual levels of *sūtra* and *bhāṣya*, he uses the terms *sūtrakāra* and *bhāṣyakāra* respectively, without mentioning a personal name; his only reference to the name Vyāsa introduces a citation from the Mahābhārata (see Maas 2006: xv). Since the author of the Vivarāṇa distinguishes *sūtrakāra* and *bhāṣyakāra*, it seems that he took the PYŚ to be the work of two different authors. It is, however, also possible that he referred to the same person with different designations.

The famous Persian scholar and polymath al-Bīrūnī composed an exposition of Hindu theology as part of his comprehensive survey of South Asian culture and sciences entitled *Fī taḥqīq mā li-l-Hind min maqūla maqbūla fī l-ʿaql aw marḍūla* (commonly referred to as *India*; see Lawrence 1990: 285) in 1030 CE. This exposition is based on the “Kitāb Bātanjal”, al-Bīrūnī’s Arabic revised translation of the PYŚ, which was completed some time before al-Bīrūnī’s *India*. The title “Kitāb Bātanjal” does not only refer to Patañjali’s Yoga Sūtra, but also the *bhāṣya* passages of the PYŚ, as can be concluded *inter alia* from the beginning of the second chapter of the *India*. There we read:

In the book of Patañjali the pupil asks: ‘Who is the worshipped one, by the worship of whom blessing is obtained?’ (Sachau 1888: 83).

This passages corresponds roughly to the introduction (*avatarāṇīkā*) of the *bhāṣya* to Yoga Sūtra I.24.

atha pradhānapuruṣavyatiriktaḥ ko ’yam īśvara iti. Who is this God being distinct from matter and self? (PYŚ I.24,1 in Maas 2006: 35).

Admittedly, al-Bīrūnī’s translation differs from the wording of the PYŚ, but this inconsistency does not necessarily indicate that he knew a different work. As was already noticed by Pines and

Gelblum,¹¹ al-Bīrūnī's translation was not a detached philological-historical enterprise. Its intention was mainly to communicate to a Muslim readership religious ideas that were intelligible and valuable according to his own criteria. Moreover, al-Bīrūnī apparently used a variety of different sources for his Kitāb Bātanjal. Nevertheless, the fact that al-Bīrūnī identifies a *bhāṣya* passage of the PYŚ to be the work of Patañjali strongly suggests that he regarded the PYŚ as a unified whole.¹² This view is supported by the fact that al-Bīrūnī never refers to Vyāsa as a commentator of the "Book of Patañjali" (see Pines/Gelblum 1966: 304); neither in his *India* nor in his translation of the PYŚ.

Pines and Gelblum, however, judged al-Bīrūnī's own testimony regarding the Sanskrit original of his translation to be contradictory.

On the one hand, in his introduction to his translation he appears to indicate that the incorporation of the commentary with the sūtras as well as the form of a dialogue are of his own making. But, on the other hand, in his conclusion he speaks of the book originally 'consisting of one thousand and a hundred questions in the form of verse'" (Pines/Gelblum 1966: 303).

Al-Bīrūnī's reference to 1100 stanzas at the end of his work does not, however, necessarily have anything to do with a real metrical work. It is much more likely that his statement is based on a scribal note in the Sanskrit manuscript he used for his translation that refers to the amount of copied text. Such notes were a standard scribal practice in Indian manuscripts. The amount is usually counted in units of thirty-two syllables called *śloka* ("a stanza or verse") or *grantha* in order to calculate the price for copying. The amount of text in 1100 *ślokas* correspond roughly to the amount of text of the PYŚ as it is transmitted, for example, in manuscript no. 622 of in the Oriental Research Institute, Thiruvananthapuram (see Maas 2006: lx). If one is willing to accept this interpretation, the seeming contradiction in al-Bīrūnī's own testimony is solved. All that remains is al-Bīrūnī's clear statement that opens his translation.

This is the beginning of the book of Patañjali, text interwoven with commentary (Pines/Gelblum 1966: 307).

¹¹ "The Arabic translation betrays a constant effort to bring the work as near as possible to the Muslim reader." Pines/Gelblum 1966: 307.

¹² Stareček (2003: 12-75) discusses this and many more agreements between al-Bīrūnī's "Book of Patañjali" and *bhāṣya* passages from the PYŚ, without, however, drawing conclusions regarding the authorship of the *bhāṣya*-passages.

Accordingly, there is no reason to doubt that al-Bīrūnī created an Arabic version of the PYŚ, which he took correctly to consist of text (*sūtra*) and commentary passages (*bhāṣya*), both making up the book (*-yogaśāstra*) of Patañjali (*pātañjala-*).

It may seem, however, that King Bhoja of Mālava, who composed a commentary exclusively on the Yoga Sūtra called Rājamārtaṇḍa around 1040 CE,¹³ had a different opinion on the authorship question of *sūtra* and *bhāṣya*. In one of his benedictory stanzas Bhoja, who ruled in Dhar, a city located in what is nowadays the western part of Madhyapradesh, compares himself with “the lord of serpents” and thereby apparently refers to the traditional mythological identification of Patañjali and the divine serpent Śeṣa (which is also frequently called Ananta; cf. below, p. 67).¹⁴ Accordingly, Bhoja likens himself to Patañjali, to whom he ascribes the authorship of one work on medicine, grammar and Yoga, respectively. The information provided in the stanza is not comprehensive enough to conclude whether Bhoja thought Patañjali had composed exclusively a *sūtra* work on Yoga, or whether he thought that Patañjali had also provided explanations in a *bhāṣya*. The fact that a Patañjali did compose a work on Kātyāyana’s *vārttikas* on Pāṇini’s Aṣṭādhyāyī and that a Patañjali is reported by some sources to have composed a commentary on a medical work (or to have revised the Carakaśaṃhitā, see HIML vol. 1a: 141-144.), could at least be taken to indicate that even Bhoja regarded Patañjali as the author of a commentary also on a Yoga work.

The assessment that Bhoja did not regard the *sūtra* passages of the PYŚ as a separate work but took them to be part of a more comprehensive whole gets support from the wording of the chapter colophons of chapters no. 2 (Sanskrit text, p. 59), 3 (Sanskrit text, p. 89), and 4 (Sanskrit text, p. 118), in which Bhoja calls his

¹³ For Bhoja’s date of see Pingree 1981: 337.

¹⁴ *Śabdānām anuśāsanam vidadhatā pātañjale kurvatā vṛttiṃ rājamṛgāṅkaśaṃjñam api ca vyātanvatā vaidyake / vākcetovapuṣaṃ malaḥ phaṇabhṛtām bhartreva yenoddhṛtas tasya śrīraṅaraṅgamallanṛpater vāco jayanty ujjvalāḥ // 5 //* (Rājendralāl Mitra 1883, Sanskrit text, p. 1). “Supreme are the splendid words of the glorious king Raṅaraṅgamalla, who like the lord of serpents extirpated the impurity of speech, mind and body when he created an authoritative work on [the use of] words, composed a commentary on the Patañjalian [work] and, moreover, produced [a work] entitled Rājamṛgāṅka on the science of medicine.”

Rājamārtaṇḍa a commentary (*vṛtti*) on the *sūtras* of the PYŚ (*pātañjalayogaśāstrasūtravṛtti*).

Arguments in favour of the hypothesis that the PYŚ was composed as a unified work do not depend only on the comparatively early literary references discussed above, but can also be derived from an analysis of the wording of the work itself.

Bronkhorst (1985) noticed differences between an unforced interpretation of Yoga Sūtras 1.21-1.23 (as well as 1.24-25 and 1.30-40) and their interpretation in the *bhāṣya*. This discrepancies indicate, according to Bronkhorst, that a single person collected the *sūtras* from older sources and provided them with his own explanations and comments in the *bhāṣya* (Bronkhorst 1985: 194). For Bronkhorst, this person could either have been Patañjali or the Sāṅkhya teacher Vindhyavāsin.

For Bronkhorst (1991: 212), the integration of *sūtras* and *bhāṣya* passages results from the endeavour of the author of the *bhāṣya* to make his work *appear* as a unified whole. However, without external evidence, it is difficult to decide whether the separation of a *sūtra* from its *bhāṣya* could not be the result of the inverse process, i.e. of the extraction of the *sūtras* from a unified work. With regard to this, it may be worth noticing that the numeration of *sūtras* in combination with a punctuation with double *daṇḍas* that we find in modern printed editions it a quite recent invention. It originates from early modern paper manuscripts.¹⁵ Older palm leaf manuscripts do not have a numeration of *sūtras* at all, they do not mark *sūtras* consistently, and they do not agree entirely with regard to the question of which parts of the work are actually *sūtras*.¹⁶

The author of the *bhāṣya* was apparently aware of the fact that some *sūtras* are older than others. In general, he introduces *sūtras* with verbs in the third person singular present passive,¹⁷ which is the

¹⁵ See Apparatus no. 3 in the critical edition of the Samādhipāda of the PYŚ in Maas 2006: 1-87, which records the punctuation and numeration of *sūtra* and *bhāṣya* passage for all collated manuscripts.

¹⁶ For example, the sentence *tasya śāstram nimittam* “The cause for it (i.e. the perfection of God) is the authoritative work” in PYŚ 1.24,11 is marked in manuscript *M*^s (serial no. 24 in Cat. Adyar) as a *sūtra*, whereas in all other manuscripts and in the printed editions it is a *bhāṣya* passage.

¹⁷ At four instances (PYŚ 2.1, 2.19, 2.20 and 2.28) the author introduces *sūtras* with the verb *ā-rabh* “to create, to compose” in its third person singular present passive

usual way for a commentator to refer to his basic text, irrespective of whether he writes a commentary on his own work or on that of a different author.¹⁸ In contrast to this procedure, the author of the *bhāṣya* part of the PYŚ introduces three *sūtras* (1.2, 1.41 and 2.23) with the verb *pravavṛte* (“was composed”), a third person singular medium in the perfect tense of the root *pra-vṛt*. Since the perfect tense is generally used to refer to events that happened in a remoter past (usually before the lifetime of a speaker)¹⁹, the *sūtras* with this peculiar introduction may be older than the *sūtras* to which the author of the *bhāṣya* refers with verbs in the present tense.

Nevertheless, there is also evidence that the author of the *bhāṣya* regarded the PYŚ as a unified whole. At five instances he uses verb forms in the first person plural of the future in the active voice²⁰ to postpone a more detailed discussion of relevant topics to latter parts of the work. He refers in this way both to *sūtras* and also to the respective *bhāṣya* parts.²¹ Moreover, quite frequently *sūtras* appear together with *bhāṣya* passages as syntactical units. For example, the beginning of PYŚ 1.5 reads

tāḥ punar niroddhavyā bahutve 'pi cittasya vṛttayaḥ pañcatayyaḥ kliṣṭākliṣṭāḥ
(YS 1.5). “These, however, which have to be stopped although they are numerous, are the activities of the mind, which are fivefold and either afflicted or unafflicted (YS 1.5).

The hypothesis that *sūtra* and *bhāṣya* passages of the PYŚ were composed as a unified whole receives support from the results of a close reading of the wording of YS 2.27 and its explanation in the *bhāṣya*. The passage runs as follows.

tasya saptadhā prāntabhūmiḥ prajñā (YS 2.27). tasyeti pratyuditakhyāteḥ
pratyāmnāyaḥ. For him, the sevenfold insight is in its final stage (YS 2.27).
“For him” is a reference to the expression “a yogi, for whom cognition has risen.”

According to the explanation of the *bhāṣya*, the pronoun *tasya* of the *sūtra* refers to the expression “a yogi, for whom cognition has risen“ (*pratyuditakhyāti*). This term refers the reader back to a

(*ārabhyate*), in PYŚ 2.17 he uses the verb *pratīnirdiśyate* “is explained,” whereas in PYŚ 2.29 he employs the present passive form *avadhāryante* “are taught.”

¹⁸ See Tubb – Boose 2007: § 2.39.4, p. 227 and § 2.39.7, p. 229.

¹⁹ See Speijer 1886: § 330, p. 247f.

²⁰ *nivedayiṣyāmaḥ* in PYŚ 1.1, *darśayiṣyāmaḥ* in 1.7, and *vakṣyāmaḥ* in 2.29, 2.40 and 2.46.

²¹ See Maas 2006: xvi and Bronkhorst 1991: 212.

passage in the *bhāṣya* on Yoga Sūtra 1.16, which is the only other instance of the word *pratyuditakhyāti* in the PYŚ. There, the highest form of freedom from craving is described in the following way.

This freedom from craving is nothing but clearness of knowledge. When it rises, a yogi, for whom cognition has risen, thinks: “I have reached what is reachable. I have destroyed all causes of distress that had to be destroyed. I have cut the succession of existences with its tight connections, which caused, as long as they were not cut, that I died after I had been born and that I was born after I had died.”²²

This passage depicts a yogi who has reached liberation in his present life, which is the same state to which Yoga Sūtra 2.27 alludes by mentioning “insight in its final stage” of development on the yogic path to liberation. From a theoretical point of view, the reference from Yoga Sūtra 2.27 to a *bhāṣya* passage in PYŚ 1.16 is therefore fully justified. The reference is also appropriate and even necessary with regard to the structure of the work, because no *sūtra* preceding Yoga Sūtra 2.27 contains a suitable referent of the pronoun *tasya*. By interpreting a pronoun of a *sūtra* to refer to a passage of the *bhāṣya* in a preceding chapter, the author of the *bhāṣya* clearly reveals that in his view the Yoga Sūtra is no literary work in its own right. For him, *sūtra* and *bhāṣya* are a single unit.²³

But does this assessment match historical facts, or does the author of the *bhāṣya* try to deceive his readers in order to make his own explanations more credible? The fact that there is indeed no suitable referent for the pronoun *tasya* of Yoga Sūtra 2.27 in any of the previous *sūtras* and that there is strong contextual connection

²² *taj jñānaprasādamātraṃ yasyodaye pratyuditakhyātir evaṃ manyate: “prāptaṃ prāpaṇīyaṃ, kṣīṇāḥ kṣetavyāḥ kleśāḥ, chinnaḥ śliṣṭaparvā bhavasamkramaḥ, yasyāvicchedāj janitvā mriyate, mṛtvā ca jāyate,” iti* (PYŚ 1.16,5 f. in Maas: 2007, 26).

²³ Śāṅkara, the author of the Pātañjalayogaśāstravivarāṇa (Vivarāṇa 205,21 f.), and Vācaspatimiśra (Āgāśe 1904: 97,17) both share this view and interpret the word *pratyuditakhyāteḥ* as a bahuvrihi referring to a yogi, whereas Vijñānabhikṣu takes this word to refer to the “means of getting rid of suffering” (*hānopāya*), which is mentioned in the previous *sūtra* 2.26. Vijñānabhikṣu’s interpretation is, however, highly problematic, because it does not take into consideration that the author of the *bhāṣya* himself explains the word *pratyuditakhyāti* as “a discerning yogi” (*vivekin*) in the immediately following passage: “*saptaparakāraiva prajñā vivekino bhavati.*” (PYŚ 2.27 Āgāśe 1904: 10).

between the *bhāṣya* in PYŚ 1.16 and Yoga Sūtra 2.27 supports the first alternative.

In view of the above discussion, Bronkhorst's hypothesis that a single person arranged the *sūtras* (some of which may originate from older sources, while others were his own composition), and furnished these *sūtras* with his own explanations and comments upon them with a *bhāṣya*, appears quite credible. If this is granted, the traditional name of the author of the *bhāṣya*, i.e. Vyāsa ("arranger" or "editor"), could be taken as a reflection of knowledge of the genesis of the PYŚ as, in part, a compilatory work.

A different tradition concerning the authorship of the PYŚ, which was brought to the attention of a broader Indological audience by Professor Dr. Ashok Aklujkar, is found in Vādirāja Sūri's commentary on Akalaṅka's Nyāyaviniścaya. Vādirāja Sūri, who composed his work around 1025 CE., holds that the *bhāṣya* passages were composed by the Sāṅkhya teacher Vindhavāsin, whereas the *sūtras* go back to Patañjali. This assessment can be harmonized with information provided by the anonymous author of the Yuktidīpikā (ca. 7th century CE?), who refers to a number of philosophical positions that agree with positions articulated in a number of *bhāṣya* passages of the PYŚ as being those of Vindhavāsin.²⁴ Moreover, in commenting on Sāṅkhyakārika 43 (Wezler – Motegi 1998: 233,20-23) the author of the Yuktidīpikā even cites a *bhāṣya* passage from PYŚ 4.12 in order to prove that Vindhavāsin denies the existence of innate, non-acquired forms of knowledge. Since this citation is introduced by the words "thus he says" (*ity āha*), it is easily conceivable that the author of the Yuktidīpikā assumed that Vindhavāsin was the author of this passage of the PYŚ or even the author of all *bhāṣya* passages of the PYŚ.

Although the Yuktidīpikā would then be the oldest source that provides information on the authorship of a (or: the) *bhāṣya* passage(s) of the PYŚ, its testimonial value appears to be weaker than that of the numerous other sources discussed above that support

²⁴ Personal communication with Prof. Ashok Aklujkar in Hamburg, autumn 2000, and Matsumoto, August 2012; cf. also Bronkhorst 1985: 206. Cf. Maas 2006: xiii. For example, the Yuktidīpikā on Sāṅkhyakārika 22 (Wezler – Motegi 1998: 187,6 f.) reports a view of Vindhavāsin on the Sāṅkhya emanation theory that agrees with the philosophical position articulated in PYŚ 2.19.

the hypothesis that a single person called Patañjali collected some *sūtras*, probably from different, now lost sources, composed most of the *sūtras* himself and provided the whole set with his own explanations in a work with the title “Pātañjala Yogaśāstra.”

In judging the credibility of this hypothesis, it may be worth remembering that in the early classical period of Indian philosophy the terms *sūtra* and *bhāṣya* did not designate different literary genres but compositional elements of scholarly works (*śāstra*). For example, the Carakasamhitā, an early classical work on Āyurveda that can be dated with some confidence to first century CE, explicitly states that “having a well designed sequence of *sūtra*-, *bhāṣya*-, and summary passages” (*suprañītasūtrabhāṣyasamgrahakrama*) is one of the qualities of a scholarly work that a prudent medical student should consider when choosing a certain *śāstra* as the basis of his education (CS Vimānasthāna 8.1, p. 261b,14).

If one accepts the PYŚ to be a unified whole, the work can be dated with some confidence to the period between 325 and 425 CE. This dating is based on the consideration that the PYŚ was widely accepted to be the authoritative exposition of Yoga at the beginning of the seventh century. Since some time has to elapse before a work achieves the status of being normative, the PYŚ may have been composed (at the latest) in the first quarter of the fifth century. The earliest limit for the date at which the work may have been composed is established by the fact that the PYŚ refers to idealist philosophical positions corresponding to those of the Vijñānavāda of Vasubandhu, who probably lived between 320 and 400 CE.²⁵ It is possible that the central philosophical theorem of Vijñānavāda is even older than Vasubandhu (Maas 2006: xviii f.).

At Bhoja’s time, i.e. in the 11th century, the tradition of a threefold authorship of one Patañjali for works on medicine, grammar and Yoga was apparently widely spread in large parts of the Indian subcontinent, since not only Bhoja, but also the Bengali commentator Cakrapāṇidatta refers to the threefold authorship in the fourth benedictory stanza of his gloss on the Carakasamhitā, the Āyurvedadīpikā (CS 1,14f., see HIML vol. 1a: loc. cit).

²⁵ Franco – Preisendanz (2010: XVI) arrived at this conclusions on the basis of a new interpretation of information that was first presented in Schmithausen 1992.

Nevertheless, as has been stressed by different Indologists before, this tradition cannot reflect historical truth. An ancient medical work of Patañjali is not known, although there exist a number of references to Patañjali that suggest he was regarded to be the author of a commentary on the Carakasamhitā or even to be Caraka himself. Moreover, the author of the grammatical Mahābhāṣya, who lived ca. 150 BCE, cannot be identical with the author of the PYŚ, since the latter Patañjali argues against the Buddhist Vijñānavāda theory that simply did not yet exist at that time.²⁶

As equally widespread as the anachronistic belief that Patañjali authored works on grammar, medicine and Yoga was apparently the idea that Patañjali was an incarnation (*avatāra*) of the divine serpent Ananta (cf. above, p. 61). This conviction manifests itself in a *maṅgala* stanza stemming from the beginning of the commentary of a certain Śaṅkara on Puruṣottamadeva's Prāṇapañita, which is a commentary on Patañjali's Mahābhāṣya. This stanza was transferred to the beginning of a version of the PYŚ in Bengal after the beginning of the twelfth century (Maas 2008: 113).

The identification of Patañjali with the divine serpent Ananta originated, according to Deshpande (1994: 113), in South India, whereas Aklujkar (2008: 73-75) argues for Kashmir as the home of this myth.

A search for records supporting a separate authorship of Patañjali and Vyāsa led me to Mādhava-Vidyāraṇya's Sarvadarśanasamgraha as providing the oldest unambiguous evidence. Mādhava's doxography from the fourteenth century was composed ca. 1.000 years after the PYŚ, and it is about 300 years younger than the above mentioned sources that indicate Patañjali's single authorship in the tenth century (cf. Maas 2006: xiif.).

This finding led me to question whether Mādhava's work could not have influenced the exposition of Yoga philosophy in secondary

²⁶ Dasgupta's (1930: 52f.) attempt to prove that the whole fourth chapter of the Yoga Sūtra is a late addition to the first three *pādas* seems to result from his wish to date the Yoga Sūtra back to a remote antiquity; and the same can be said about Prasad (1930: 371ff.), who takes upaniṣadic – and not Buddhist – theories to be the target of Patañjali's polemics; cf. also Jacobi 1930b: 82 and 86, and Maas 2006: xviii. On linguistic differences reflecting a historical distance between the Mahābhāṣya and the Yoga Sūtra, see Renou 1940.

literature even beyond the treatment of the authorship question. When I started to pursue this subject, however, it soon turned out that I was on the wrong track. As far as I can see now, the *Sarvadarśanasamgraha* had no effect worth mentioning on the exposition of Yoga in modern secondary literature. Indian doxographical literature may, however, be responsible for the very fact that Yoga in modern histories of Indian philosophy was treated as a separate school of thought, since the division of orthodox classical Indian philosophies into Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika, Sāṅkhya-Yoga, and Mīmāṃsā-Vedānta, which is generally accepted today, may first have been developed by doxographic authors. According to Halbfass, this division probably occurred for the first time in the *Sarvadarśana-kaumudī* by Mādhava Sarasvatī (Halbfass 1990: 353),²⁷ who “in all probability flourished in the first half of the sixteenth century” (Dasgupta 1922-1955, vol. 2: 250).

Other doxographies and works with doxographic information that do not deal with the Yoga school of thought separately may refer to Yoga as a sub-school of Sāṅkhya. Mādhava-Vidyāraṇya refers to Yoga as *seśvara-sāṅkhya*, i.e. “*sāṅkhya-with-a-lord*”, because the system integrates a high god into its metaphysical inventory, which is otherwise identical to that of classical Sāṅkhya (SDS 333,6-334,2); but according to earlier sources the advocates of *seśvara-sāṅkhya* and *nirīśvara-sāṅkhya* differ with regard to the question as to whether or not a high god is involved in the periodical creation and dissolution of the world (cf. Bronkhorst 1983 and Hattori 1999).

Even the fact that modern histories of Indian philosophy frequently mention Vyāsa or Vedavyāsa as the author of the *bhāṣya*-part of the PYŚ cannot be attributed to a direct influence of the *Sarvadarśanasamgraha*. The information of Vyāsa’s alleged authorship presumably stems from the chapter colophons of printed editions and also from the second introductory stanzas of Vācaspatimiśra’s *Tattvavaiśārādī*, which can be dated to around 950 CE (Acharya 2006: xxviii; cf. also Maas 2006: xii). As I have argued in the introduction of my critical edition (Maas 2006: xiv-xvii), Vācaspati’s oeuvre, as far as it is presently available in printed editions, contains contradictory information on the authorship question, and any hints contained in the colophons of printed editions stem from compa-

²⁷ Halbfass’ work has been partly superseded by Gerschheimer 2007.

ratively recent paper manuscripts of the PYŚ. The original source of information for Vyāsa's alleged authorship is unknown to me. It could be a reflection of the memory that a single person called Patañjali collected some *sūtras* from older sources, composed some *sūtras* himself, arranged (*vi + √as*) the *sūtra* part of the *śāstra* and provided it with his own philosophical explanations which later came to be known as the Yoga Bhāṣya.

Irrespective of the question of whether the PYŚ has a single author – and irrespective of how to define “authorship” for a literary work consisting of different textual layers – it is advisable from a philological and historical point of view to accept, at least hypothetically, that this work is the result of single, roughly datable philosophical authorial intention. The *sūtra* part taken for itself consists of 195 (or, in other versions, of 196) brief statements that in some cases are not even full sentences. Because of the brevity of these statements and because of the shortness of the *sūtra* part as a whole, the Yoga Sūtra cannot be interpreted convincingly without taking recourse to its historical and cultural contexts. As we shall see below, the text-immanent approach to the Yoga Sūtras was indeed used frequently to project anachronistic ideas upon this text.

3. THE HISTORY OF INDOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON THE PĀTAÑJALA YOGAŚĀSTRA

As we have seen above, the first Indological publication on classical Yoga philosophy was Henry Thomas Colebrooke's essay “On the philosophy of the Hindus” (Colebrooke 1827). Colebrooke introduced his readers not only to the Yoga Sūtra but also to the Yoga Bhāṣya, which he attributed to an author named Vyāsa. Moreover, he referred to two (sub-)commentaries of the PYŚ, Vācaspatimiśra's *Tattvavaiśarādī* (ca. 950-1000 CE, see Acharya 2006: xxviii) and to the *Yogavārttika* of Vijñānabhikṣu from the latter half of the sixteenth century CE (see Larson/Bhattacharya 1984: 376).

The first printed translation of a part of the Yoga Sūtra was, however, based on neither of these commentaries. Ballantyne edited the first two chapters of this work together with extracts from Bhoja's *Rājamārtaṇḍa* (ca. 1040 CE, see Pingree 1981: 337) and published it in 1852 and 1853, along with the English translation that

he had prepared jointly with *paṇḍits* from Benares (Ballantyne 1852). Ballantyne was aware of the fact that his work was rather provisional and in need of revision. He explicitly stated that he was unable to secure the support of any *paṇḍita* with expert knowledge on yoga (Ballantyne 1852: ii).

After Ballantyne's death, his translation was continued by Govinda Deva Shastrin (also called Govind Shastri Deva) who rendered chapters three and four into English and published them in the periodical *The Pandit* [O.S.], Vol. 3-6, fasc. 28-67 (1868-1871). Ballantyne's and Shastrin's translations were revised by Tookaram Tātya and reprinted in a single volume for the Theosophical Society in 1885 (Tātya 1885), just two years after Rājendralāl Mitra had published a complete edition and translation of the Yoga Sūtra together with Bhoja's commentary in 1883. Mitra, however, apparently misjudged the philosophical importance and the date of the *bhāṣya* passages of the PYŚ, since he took the "tone of the Bhaṣya ... [to be] that of a third class mediæval scholium" that would have to be dated to "the latest ancient times, or, more probably, the early middle ages" (Mitra 1883: lxxx).

In the meantime, Jibananda Vidyasagara had edited and published the PYŚ in print together with Vācaspatimiśra's commentary (Vidyasagara 1874). A few years later, in 1883-1884, Rāmakṛṣṇa Śāstrī and Keśava Sāstrī published the *editio princeps* of Vijnānabhikṣu's Yogavārttika in Varanasi (Śāstrī – Sāstrī 1883) in *The Pandit* [N.S.].²⁸ In the following years, several editions of the PYŚ together with the Tattvavaiśārādī appeared. Among these, the Ānādāśrama edition by K.Ś. Agāṣe of 1904, which also included the Rājamārtaṇḍa (Agāṣe 1904), and Rajaram Shastri Bodas' edition in the revised version by Vasudev Shastri Abhyankar of 1917 (Bodas 1917) deserve particular mention, because both editions report selected variant readings from several paper manuscripts and printed editions in their footnotes.²⁹

The knowledge of Yoga philosophy increased considerably towards the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century.

²⁸ As far as I know, Rukmani (1981-1989) prepared the only complete translation of this work into English.

²⁹ For details on thirty-seven editions of the Pātañjala Yogaśāstra, cf. Maas 2006: xxii-xxxvi.

Especially noteworthy are some landmark studies, like, Garbe's *Sāṃkhya und Yoga* (Garbe 1896), Müller's *The Six Systems of Indian Philosophy* (Müller 1899), the first complete English translation of the PYŚ by Ganganatha Jha (Jha 1907), the monumental translation of the same work together with the *Tattvavaiśārādī* by Woods (1914), and Strauss' *Indische Philosophie* (Strauss 1925). Jacobi and Dasgupta, too, published widely on classical Yoga in the 1920s and 1930s.³⁰ The histories of Indian philosophy of this period are, however, still similar to Sanskrit doxographies in that they present different schools of thought separately and without giving much attention to their mutual influences throughout South Asian intellectual history.

A remarkable exception from the doxographical approach to Yoga philosophy appears in the two works of Émil Senart (1900) and Louis de la Vallée Poussin (1937), who instigated an ongoing discussion about the historical relationship of Yoga and Buddhism in general and on the structure of their respective meditations.

In this connection also the work of Lindquist on the miraculous powers of yoga (Lindquist 1935), which also compares the PYŚ with Pāli Buddhist sources, deserves to be mentioned.³¹ The topic of Yoga powers received just recently fresh attention in a volume of collected papers edited by Jacobsen (2012).

Systematic in-depth studies of the relationship between classical Yoga and Buddhism on the one hand, as well as on the relationship between Yoga and Jainism on the other, remain, however, *desiderata*.

As mentioned above (p. 61), the PYŚ was the most important source for al-Bīrūnī's description of Hindu theology in his *India* (dating from 1030), which became accessible to a larger academic public through the English translation by Sachau (Sachau 1888). Al-Bīrūnī also prepared a quite liberal translation of the PYŚ entitled "Book of Patañjali" into Arabic some time before he completed his

³⁰ Cf., for example, Jacobi 1929, 1930a, 1930b and Dasgupta 1920, 1922-1955, 1930.

³¹ Lindquist had published a detailed study on yoga methods in 1932, which suffers, however, from his unconvincing equation of yogic states of meditation with hypnosis.

encyclopaedic work. This Arabic version was translated and richly annotated by Pines and Gelblum between 1966 and 1989.³²

One of the most widely read works on yoga ever published is without doubt Mircea Eliade's "Yoga: Imortality and Freedom" (1958; the original French version was published in 1954). The long history of Eliade's writing of his book began when the twenty-three-year old Romanian scholar studied Sanskrit with Dasgupta in Calcutta for twenty-one months in 1929 and 1930. Eliade fell into the disgrace of his teacher because of his liaison with Dasgupta's sixteen-year old daughter Maitreyi (Guggenbühl 2008: 15). After leaving Dasgupta's house, Eliade got himself trained in practical yoga for six months in Rishikesh, before he resumed his academic studies with a special emphasis on Tantric forms of yoga (Guggenbühl 2008: 24). Eliade was not particularly interested in Yoga philosophy, about which – he thought – everything relevant had already been said by Dasgupta.

Mircea Eliade's *Yoga* was well received and it appears to be one of the most frequently cited works on yoga to the present date (Guggenbühl 2008: 6). As was noted by Hacker in his review of the German translation of *Yoga*, the work presents a lot of formerly unknown material from the Hindu Tantras, and it is often thought-provoking and original. On the other hand, Eliade's religious phenomenology remains frequently superficial and unaware of specific contexts.³³

The doxographical approach to Indian philosophy, which characterized the early phase of Indological research in Yoga philosophy, was later also partly given up in the first volume of Frauwallner's "Geschichte der indischen Philosophie" (Frauwallner 1953). This work is without doubt a climax in the historiography of Yoga philosophy. Frauwallner draws a coherent picture of the historical development of Yoga from the time of pre-systematic philosophy up

³² Pines/Gelblum 1966, 1977, 1983 and 1989. For details on the earlier history of research in al-Bīrūnī's "Book of Patañjali" see Pines/Gelblum 1966: 302f.

³³ Hacker 1962: 318: "Eine Methode, die die Worte und Dinge so läßt, wie sie in ihrem Kontext vorgefunden werden, ist doch als Grundlage unerläßlich, wenn die Wissenschaft nicht zur geistreichen Willkür werden soll." "A method that leaves words and things as they are found in their context is indispensable as a basis if academic studies shall not turn into clever arbitrariness."

to its classical period by showing different philosophical schools in their mutual intellectual relationship. Moreover, Frauwallner's very clear presentation of classical Yoga philosophy – as well as that of other philosophical schools – is based on his generally admirable knowledge of primary sources.

Unfortunately, however, Frauwallner does not refer his reader as closely to the primary sources of Yoga as one might wish. Moreover, the narrative structure of Frauwallner's exposition suffers from his rather simplistic explanations of philosophical developments whenever he was apparently unable to derive satisfactory explanations from his sources.³⁴ In addition, Frauwallner was not very sensitive to the psychological aspects of Yoga philosophy, especially with regard to the structure of different forms of meditation (cf. Maas 2009: 264f.). This lack of sensitivity or interest may be the result of his approach towards Yoga, which is characterized by favouring aspects of the PYŚ that can be labelled as “theoretical yoga philosophy” over those belonging to yoga practice.

A new chapter of research in Yoga philosophy was opened with the publication of the first complete edition of the Pātañjalayoga-śāstravivaraṇa,³⁵ a commentary of the Yoga Sūtra together with the *bhāṣya* by Polakam Sri Rama Sastri and S.R. Krishnamurthi Sastri in Madras 1952. This was one year before Frauwallner's “*Geschichte*” appeared, but still too late to be utilized in it. The textual quality of the *editio princeps* of the Vivaraṇa was not very high, because the work was edited on the basis of a single, quite corrupt Malayālam palm leaf manuscript. To improve the text, the editors provided the edition with their own emendations and conjectures, which they did not, however, indicate consistently (see Wezler 1983: 18f.).

In spite of all the philological shortcomings of this edition, the philosophical and historical relevance of this newly-available work for studies in yoga philosophy was soon recognized by Hacker in

³⁴ See for example Frauwallner's explanation of the fact that classical Yoga accepts only one mental capacity (*citta*), instead of three in classical Sāṅkhya. “Vindhyavāsī hatte die altertümliche Lehre von den drei psychischen Organen ... aufgegeben” (Frauwallner 1953: 411). We simply do not know whether Yoga accepts a single mental capacity because the triple differentiation was taken to be outdated.

³⁵ S.K. Rāmanātha Śāstri had edited a part of the work before, which he published as early as 1931 as an appendix to his edition of Maṇḍanamiśra's Sphoṭasiddhi; see Halbfass 1991: 206.

1960 (col. 526f.; more pronouncedly in Hacker 1968), and afterwards by scholars like Mayeda (1968-1969: 239, and 1979: 4 and 65 note 63), Schmithausen (1968-1969: 331), Oberhammer (1977: 135), Vetter (1979: 21), Nakamura (1980-1981 and 2004), Halbfass (1983 and 1991), Wezler (1982, 1983, 1984a, 1984b, 1986, 1987 and 2001), and Bronkhorst (1985: 195).³⁶ To put it briefly, the *Vivaraṇa* has been used as an important source of information by leading Indologists for more than fifty years.

The discovery of this work was not only important for the study of Indian philosophy in the more narrow scope of Yoga, but also in a wider context. The chapter colophons of the *Vivaraṇa* state the author of the work to be a certain ŚrīGovindaBhagatpūjayapādaśiṣya Paramahamsaparivrājaka ŚrīŚaṅkarabhagavat (or -bhagavatpāda). This indicates that the *Vivaraṇa* might be the work of the famous Advaita Vedāntin Śaṅkara, author of the *Brahmasūtrabhāṣya*, whose formal title this is. The editors of the first edition of the *Vivaraṇa* made a rather premature commitment in favour of this guess.

Paul Hacker published a brief study in 1947 on the authorship problem of the many works allegedly authored by Śaṅkara. He found out that any work naming its author Śaṅkarabhagavat in a colophon is more likely to be authentic than a work that calls its author Śaṅkarācārya. Hacker's study was, however, not based on the evidence of manuscript colophons directly, but on the information provided by just seven catalogues, only two of which contained more comprehensive information (Hacker 1947: 7).

In an article published in the *Festschrift* dedicated to Frauwallner, Hacker showed that a number of peculiarities in Śaṅkara's Advaita Vedānta led him to the conclusion that the famous Advaitin was influenced by Yoga philosophy. From this judgement, Hacker developed the hypothesis that Śaṅkara was a yogi in his youth before he converted to Advaita Vedānta (Hacker 1968). Hacker's conversion hypothesis was not, however, intended to prove that the *Vivaraṇa* is an authentic work of the famous Advaitin Śaṅkara (cf. Halbfass 1991: 207); "it rather pre-supposed the identity of the two authors" (Wezler 1983: 36).

³⁶ Cf. Halbfass 1991: 205f.

Halbfass (1991: 215ff.) highlighted a number of striking similarities between philosophical arguments in Śaṅkara's commentary on the Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad and in the Vivaraṇa. On the other hand, he showed convincingly (1991: 224-228) that Śaṅkara's attitude towards Sāṅkhya metaphysics and Yoga soteriology, as it is evident in his major works, is basically irreconcilable with the teachings of the PYŚ. Śaṅkara's hypothetical turn from Yoga philosophy to Advaita Vedānta therefore presupposes a far-reaching new orientation of personal beliefs of this philosopher. Even if one concedes that such a radical change of philosophical allegiance is possible in a person's early life, the discrepancy of world views in Yoga and Advaita Vedānta make Śaṅkara's authorship of the Vivaraṇa appear quite improbable.

A final solution of the authorship question, in contrast to Rukmani's unfounded claim to have solved the problem (1998), can only be reached by a comprehensive analysis and comparison of the respective styles of writing in the works under consideration, for which critical editions of Śaṅkara's main works as well as of the Vivaraṇa would be necessary preconditions.

Irrespective of the authorship problem, the Vivaraṇa is an important source of knowledge for Yoga philosophy. This has been established by the numerous studies mentioned above (p. 73). It explains difficult passages of the PYŚ on which Vācaspati's Tattvavaiśārādī remains silent and reflects important philosophical debates between Sāṅkhya-Yoga on the one hand, and Buddhist and orthodox Hindu schools of thought on the other. The role of the Vivaraṇa for the interpretation of the PYŚ may be compared to that of the Yuktidīpikā (Wezler – Motegi 1998) for understanding the philosophy of the Sāṅkhya Kārikās.

The Vivaraṇa has not yet been dated with certainty, but Halbfass showed that the most recent author to whom this work clearly refers is Kumāriḷa, who lived in the seventh century (Halbfass 1983: 120). Moreover, the version of the PYŚ commented on in the Vivaraṇa preserves ancient readings which are nowadays lost in many, if not in all available manuscripts (see Maas 2006: lxix). Nothing, therefore, hinders the assumption that the Vivaraṇa is much closer to the PYŚ, not only in content but also historically, than the Tattvavaiśārādī from the middle of the tenth century.

This assessment has met the opposition of Rukmani, who proposes a rather late date of the Vivaraṇa and claims that this work contains “some explicit reference to Vācaspati Mīśra’s statements” in the Tattvavaiśārādī (Rukmani 1998: 267). This view has to be rejected, because the Vivaraṇa passages discussed by Rukmani do not sufficiently support her claim. In my view, an “explicit reference” would constitute one of three things: (1) A reference to Vācaspati by name or by the title of his work, or (2) a literal citation from the Tattvavaiśārādī, or (3) a citation giving the gist of a statement which can be identified as Vācaspati’s own genuine and innovative interpretation of a passage from the base text, or a reference to an altogether new philosophical position of Vācaspati. In other words, an “explicit reference” should be genuinely unambiguous. None of the Vivaraṇa passages discussed by Rukmani matches any of these criteria. Nevertheless, her dating of the Vivaraṇa between the eleventh and the fourteenth century was adopted in the “Yoga” volume of the Encyclopaedia of Indian Philosophies without much reservation (Larson – Bhattacharya 2008: 239), although Harimoto (2004: 179f.) had shown seven years earlier (in his review of Rukmani 2001) that Rukmani’s arguments for the alleged familiarity of the author of the Vivaraṇa with Vācaspatimīśra’s work are flawed.

The publication of the first complete edition of the Vivaraṇa in print paved the way for another major achievement in the history of research in philosophical Yoga, i.e. Oberhammer’s *Strukturen yogischer Meditation* (Oberhammer 1977). Oberhammer convincingly explains, for the first time, the psychology of yogic meditations by almost exclusively drawing upon information from the PYŚ together with the Vivaraṇa. He shows that the PYŚ teaches four kinds of yogic meditations which differ from each other with regard to their respective objects of meditation as well as with regard to their structure, i.e. in the treatment (or development) of content of consciousness within meditation.

The first kind of meditation has the subject (*puruṣa*) as its object. It is characterized by a systematic reduction of consciousness content that leads from an intensive encounter with Yoga teachings about the true nature of the subject to an unrestricted self-awareness (Oberhammer 1977: 135-161; see also Maas: 2009: 264-276). The second kind of meditation is a theistic variant of the first. Its object of meditation is a personal high god, whose identity with the individual

self is realized in the course of an interplay between meditation and mantra-repetition (Oberhammer 1977: 162-177; see also Maas: 2009: 276-280). The third kind of meditation, the so-called *samāpatti*, is a variety of a direct perception, in which the content of a memory substitutes the visible object. In the course of meditation, the consciousness content consisting of the remembered object is reduced to ever finer levels of existence – according to the inversed scheme of the Sāṅkhya-emanation doctrine – until the object of meditation is finally reduced to primordial (or rather proto-)matter (*prakṛti*), which is thought to be beyond being and non-being. This reduction of content weakens the wrong identification of the self with the ontological realm of matter and leads to final liberation after the physical death of the yogi (Oberhammer 1977: 177-209). The fourth kind of meditation treated in the PYŚ was inherited by classical Yoga from earlier ascetic movements, which aimed at accumulating of magical powers rather than at liberation from rebirth. (Oberhammer 1977: 209-230).

Although Oberhammer's work was very favourably reviewed by Alper (1980) and Olivelle (1980) – who, by the way, both wrote in English – the *Strukturen* has never received the attention it still deserves. A case in point is the volume on *Yoga* in the *Encyclopaedia of Indian Philosophies*, which refers to Oberhammer's work so superficially that one wonders whether the authors read it carefully enough. Larson – Bhattacharya (2008) refer to Oberhammer's *Strukturen* only in one unnumbered footnote on p. 52, which wrongly states that Oberhammer follows Frauwallner (1953) in accepting basically two types of meditation, i.e. “the ‘eight-limbed Yoga (of YS II and III) (*der Weg des achtgliedrigen Yoga*) and the Yoga of the cessation of cognitive functioning (*der Weg der Unterdrückung der Geistestätigkeit*) (YS I).” This wrong representation of Oberhammer's work is all the more regrettable since Oberhammer not only deals with formerly unexplored aspects of Yoga psychology, but also contributes to solving the riddle of the PYŚ's difficult composition. The structure of the PYŚ appears to be roughly in accordance with the four kinds of meditation discussed by Oberhammer.

The publication of the first complete printed edition of the Vivaraṇa not only stimulated research into Yoga philosophy, but also into the textual history of the PYŚ. Already the editors of the Vivaraṇa

had noticed that this work comments upon a text that differs from the version presented in modern printed editions, but they did not pursue the matter consistently. Instead, their edition of the PYŚ is basically a copy of the Ānandāśrama edition (Āgāṣe 1904, or one of its reprints) into which the editors inserted selected readings from the Vivaraṇa's basic text.

As early as in 1983, Wezler drew attention to the fact that many more ancient readings of the PYŚ can be reconstructed from the Vivaraṇa than were detected by the editors (Wezler 1983). The philological and philosophical importance of the Vivaraṇa justifies a new critical edition of this work, especially since Wezler discovered a second Malayālam manuscript in the Woolner Collection and Punjab University Library, Lahore (serial no. 428, Ma in vol. 2 of Ram 1932-1941). Kengo Harimoto began this work and submitted a new critical edition of the first chapter of the Vivaraṇa as his PhD thesis in 1999 (Harimoto 1999). Unfortunately, he has not yet published his work in print.

This new achievement was therefore overlooked by Rukmani, who prepared a complete English translation of the Vivaraṇa on the basis of her own edition, which is nothing more than a copy of the Madras edition from 1952 (Rukmani 2001: ix) to which Rukmani added her own scribal mistakes. Rukmani was also not aware of Leggett's earlier translation of the Vivaraṇa (Leggett 1990, which supersedes his own previous partial translation in Leggett 1981-1983). Neither Leggett's nor Rukmani's translation are entirely satisfactory from a scholarly perspective.³⁷

Wezler's preliminary assessment of the textual quality of the basic text of the Vivaraṇa was supported by the results of my investigation into the written transmission of the PYŚ, which was published in 2006 together with a critical edition of the PYŚ's Samādhīpāda and a reconstruction of the Vivaraṇa's base text, the latter being prepared partly in collaboration with Kengo Harimoto (Maas 2006).

The result of my text-genealogical research (cf. Maas 2010) can be summed up as follows. The PYŚ has come down to us in two main branches of transmission which transmit the southern and the northern version. The split of the transmission must have happened

³⁷ See the reviews of Leggett's work by de Jong (1994: 63) and Gelblum (1992: 79-84) and Harimoto's review of Rukmani's translation (Harimoto 2001).

before ca. 950 CE, when Vācaspati Mīśra composed his *Tattvavaiśārādī*.³⁸ The northern version is transmitted in all printed editions, in all available paper manuscripts and in a palm leaf manuscript in Old Bengali script. The southern version is transmitted in the basic text of the *Vivaraṇa*, in palm leaf manuscripts in Telugu, Grantha and Malayālam script as well as in two ancient palm leaf manuscripts from Gujarat and Rajasthan, photographs of which became available to me just recently thanks to the good office of my colleague Dr. Yasutaka Muroya.³⁹ On the basis of textual witnesses from both main branches of the transmission, it is possible to reconstruct a quite early version of the PYŚ, the textual quality of which is much higher than that of the individual manuscripts and previous printed editions.

Taking into consideration the present state of research, it is easy to define the future tasks of Yoga studies. A first step would be the completion of the critical edition of the PYŚ as well as the preparation of reliable critical editions of the *Vivaraṇa*, the *Tattvavaiśārādī* and Vijñānabhikṣu's *Yogavārttika*, which will provide the basis for scholarly annotated English translations.⁴⁰ Once achieved, these editions could be used to fine-tune our knowledge of classical Yoga, as well as that of the intellectual influences between classical Yoga and other philosophical and religious schools of thought.

Future studies in Yoga philosophy will be particularly promising when they give up the doxographical approach completely. This will help to develop into a commonplace the hermeneutical insight that

³⁸ This can be concluded from the fact that Vācaspati comments upon the secondary reading *svarūpadarśana* in PYŚ I.29, where the southern version preserves the more original *svapurūṣadarśana*. Vācaspati glosses the compound *svarūpa* with *svam ātmā tasya rūpam* (Agāṣe 1904: 33,23); cf. Maas 2006: 45 and Maas 2010: 166.

³⁹ These are manuscript no. 395/2 (*Jinabhadrasūri tāḍapatrīya graṁth bhaṁḍāra-jaisalmer durg*) in Jambuvijaya 2000, which is dated to 1143/44 CE, according to the catalogue, and the uncatalogued manuscript no. 344A in the Lalbhai Dalpatbhai Bharatiya-Sanskriti-Vidya-Mandir, Ahmedabad. The very discovery of these two manuscripts containing the southern version in north India calls for the invention of a new designation for the so-called southern version.

⁴⁰ Filliozat's translation of the *Pātañjala Yogaśāstra* (2005), although a useful work of scholarship, does not fulfil all scholarly requirements. It is based on the vulgate version of the *Pātañjala Yogaśāstra*, its annotations are mainly intended for a more general readership, and it does not use the explanations of the *Vivaraṇa*.

Yoga philosophy is much more than Sāṅkhya theory combined with soteriological practice.

From a synchronic perspective, the PYŚ is well integrated in classical Indian philosophical discourse. The work reflects debates between the proponents of Sāṅkhya-Yoga on the one hand and the Sautrāntika and Sarvāstivāda schools of Śrāvakayāna Buddhism on the other. Moreover, the work contains polemics against the early Yogācāra school of Mahāyāna Buddhism, which are elaborated in the Vivaraṇa. Moreover, since the PYŚ was influenced in its own philosophical positions by Buddhist philosophies, a systematic evaluation of these influences would “finally contribute, of course, to a better understanding of the complex interrelation between Hinduism and Buddhism in India.”⁴¹

Within the realm of the so-called orthodox brahmanical philosophy, the PYŚ enters into polemic discussions with the philosophical school of the grammarians, with Mīmāṃsā, Nyāya and Vaiśeṣika. These discussions are also comprehensively reflected in the Vivaraṇa (see Gelblum 1992: 77).

Further studies of the PYŚ will also be fruitful for our knowledge of the general history of Indian philosophy, because the work cites the ancient Sāṅkhya works of Jaiḡṣavya and Vārṣagaṇya that, besides these citations (and citations or references in other works), are entirely lost.⁴² Moreover, in a quite cursory search, I could find citations of the Samādhipāda, i.e. first chapter of the PYŚ, in more than thirty Sanskrit works, most of them belonging to the school of Kashmir Śaivism. Apparently, the PYŚ remained an important reference work for South Asian philosophers even when Sāṅkhya-Yoga had ceased to be a creative factor in Indian philosophy.

4. CONCLUSION

Even after two-hundred years of scholarship, Indological research in classical Yoga is still in its infancy. As we have seen above, basic philological work, like the publication of historically reliable editions

⁴¹ Wezler 1987: 377 (my translation). The wording of the German original is: “würde letztlich natürlich auch zu einem besseren Verständnis der komplexen Wechselbeziehung zwischen Hinduismus und Buddhismus in Indien beitragen.”

⁴² See, for example, Garbe 1893 and Takagi 1963.

and the preparation of scholarly annotated translations, needs still to be done. The reasons for this unsatisfactory state of research are by and large the same as those for similar situations in other fields of Indian philosophy: the long standing exclusion of Indian philosophy from the history of philosophy (on which see Halbfass 1990: 145-159), the decline of interest in text based studies from the 60s of the last century onwards (see Pollock 2009), and insufficient funding of Indological studies in the academic world as a whole.⁴³ Nevertheless, due to the large public attention that yoga receives in globalized societies, the consequences of this unsatisfactory state of research in yoga studies may be not only of academic but also of social and political relevance. At the time being, the public interest in yoga is, at least in part, channelled and satisfied by amateurs and self-designated representatives of “the yoga tradition,” who propagate religious and partly right-wing Hindu fundamentalist ideas disguised as knowledge (for an example of propaganda masked as scholarship, see Sinha 1992). This situation clearly calls for comprehensive and well sustained multidisciplinary academic research, for which philological and historical studies can provide a solid foundation.

ABBREVIATIONS AND LITERATURE

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